

CHRISTIAN MISSIONARIES AND THE FORGING OF MODERN SANTAL IDENTITY: LANGUAGE, LITERACY, AND CULTURAL PRESERVATION IN COLONIAL INDIA

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ABSTRACT:

Myth of creation is the central locus for Santal identity. After the advent of Christian missionaries in India in general and particularly in the Santal soil they played pivotal role among the Santal tribe. In the context of the changing nature of India's relationship with her tribal Adivasi population, this paper seeks to analyze the role of Christian missionaries through their written ethnographic accounts made attempts to construct the Santal identity and how they came into contact with this periphery and influenced them. This paper also seeks to analyse the oral tradition of the creation myth that has been passed on from generation to generation which sustain the identity of Santal. In this article, I will explore the role of various missionaries and the implication of their methods to transform this tribe. Language, Culture and Religion play important role in any society that define its distinctiveness and its identity.

KEYWORDS:

SANTAL, CHRISTIAN MISSIONARIES, IDENTITY, HEATHEN.

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INTRODUCTION:

The Santals number about 6.57 million according to the census of 2011 and mostly inhabit in India, Bangladesh and Nepal. In India, they are mostly found in Jharkhand, West Bengal, Orissa and Bihar. According to Sreksfrud the word Santal is a corruption of the word

Saontar. Ordinarily they call themselves hor (man). The Santals speak Santali, which belongs to the Munda group of languages of the Austro-Asiatic language family. According to Andersen, the Santals have been recognised as a separate ethnic group since the end of the 18th century and since the advent of British rule in India an overwhelmingly rich documentary source of material is available about them. The missionary work among the Santals was commenced around 1850 and gradually the missionaries conceived unanimous adaptation of writing the Santali language in Roman script. Several scholars contest the use of the term "tribe" claiming that the distinction between tribe and caste is a colonial invention. The popular image of the Adivasi of India as isolated, primitive, barbaric and uncivilized. James Scott says, why did civilization not reach the hills and forest? Bhangya Bhukya claim that the colonial rulers dubiously created an administrative divide between the plains and the hills, and typified hill and forest communities as isolated, primitive, barbaric and civilized. G. S. Ghurye states that the tribes of India are Backward Hindus. However, no tribes of India themselves claim that they belong to Hindus religious group. The Christian

missionaries hailed from European counties like Scotland and Norway initiated missionary work among the Santals and elevated the condition of poor Santal. They fought for the human rights of Santal, established educational institutions, also introduced new religion among the heathen and contributed intellectual works. Therefore, it is a new identity distinct from the former.

CHRISTIAN MISSIONARIES AND THEIR ROLE OF CONSTRUCTING NEW IDENTITY.

Before the advent of Christian missionaries the Santals were looked upon down by the other communities what Bhangya Bhukya claims people from the plain. The missionary work among the Santals was began around 1850 and gradually the missionaries adapted of writing the Santali language in Roman script. Among the missionary scholars, the work of Lars Olsen Skreksrud and Paul Olaf Bodding stand unparalleled. Both of these pioneers collected most of their data from areas around Dumka in the Santal Parganas of Jharkhand and Benagaria of West Bengal. L.O. Skreksrud from his arrival in 1869 up to his death in 1910 and P.O. Bodding from his arrival in 1890 until he returned to Scandinavia in 1934 served for the upliftment of the Santals. Skreksrud and Bodding worked on a wide range of topics such as grammar, lexicography, folklore, anthropological descriptions of the Santals, Bible translation and Christian hymn and prayers.

Bodding's *Santal Dictionary*, published in five volumes between 1932 and 1936 is the legacy left behind him. It was based on Skrefsrud's vocabulary of 13,000 words which had been more than doubled during Bodding's own work. This dictionary contains a valuable source of information about the Santals. W.G. Archer one of the British colonial administrator was appointed Deputy Commissioner of the Santal Parganas in December 1942. After two and half years of his service learnt Santali language and wrote a collection of Santal poetry, legends and stories.

REV. JEREMIAH PHILLIPS:

Jeremiah Phillips belongs to the Free Will Baptist Foreign Mission Society of New Hampshire in the USA. He made first contact with Santals in 1836. After becoming well versed in Santali language he first made an attempt to write Santali grammar in 1852. Rev. J. Phillips, in his book "An Introduction to the Santali Language: Consisting of a Grammar, Reading Lessons, and a Vocabulary" mentions "The Santal, having been hitherto an unwritten language, has, of course, no characters of its own, by which to represent articulate sounds. To supply this deficiency, the Bengali alphabet has, for obvious reasons, been adopted". Rev. J. Phillips, who lived in Orissa, published a book entitled "An Introduction to the Santal Language" in 1852. It consists of a grammar, some reading and lessons and a Vocabulary. This is perhaps the first book in Santali that appeared in print.

REV. LARS OLSEN SKREFSRUD:

Rev. Lars Olsen Skrefsrud was a member of Northern Evangelical Church. In 1863, he left for India, where he joined the Baptist E. C. Johnson to work among the Santals of India. In 1867, Benagaria Mission was established among the Santals. Behind the establishment of Benagaria Mission, Skrefsrud had a great contribution. In 1873 the Rev. L. O. Skrefsrud edited "A Grammar of the Santali Language", a work which has been the foundation of all the later works on this language. The oldest and most authoritative accounts of Santal history and traditions available so far are those told by Kolean Guru, an old preceptor of the Santals, to Rev. L. O. Skrefsrud, the pioneer Norwegian missionary to the Santals. N. N. Rønning, who wrote about Skrefsrud in a biography published by the Santal Mission in America, summarized that the respect was earned because he went forth from poverty and prison and became one of the great missionaries of modern times. Mr. Skrefsrud has finely recorded the account of Santal history in the introductory part of his book "A Grammar of the Santal Language".

REV. A. CAMPBELL:

Rev. A. Campbell was inspired to come to India by Alexander Duffak, the head of Free Church of Scotland in 1873. He came in contact with the Santals when he was stationed in Pachamba between 1873 to 1879, then moved to Pokharia Mission in Manbhum. Campbell established a printing machine, to bring out Santali books to facilitate Santal students to study in Santali language. He himself

wrote the Santali books and got them printed from his own printing machine. Campbell's edited books are like "Santali Parhao Puṭhi" (I, II & III) (Santali Study Books, I, II & III). Besides these books, he brought out books like "Paha Poho", "Piyañ Payañ", "Kuli o Acur". He translated the Old Testament of Bible into Santali language. Overall, the greatest contribution of Campbell was "A Santali English Dictionary" which was published in 1899. He composed many Santali songs. Collection of Santali songs of Campbell and others were compiled together under the title "Pokharia Sereñ Puṭhi" (Pokharia Song Book), which was published in 1883.

REV. PAUL OLAF BODDING:

A young Norwegian missionary called Paul Olaf Bodding came to India in January 1890. He devoted most of his time for the development of Santali literature and was responsible for improving written Santali language. He lived at Mohulpahari more than thirty years. Bodding published more than twenty-five works on the Santals. He was very much interested in the mythologies, legends, folk tales, songs, witchcraft, medicines, and daily life of Santals. The Santali Magazine "Hoṛ Hopon -ren Pera" (the Guest of the Santals), which was brought out monthly from Benagaria Mission, was purely because of his love and passion for the growth of Santali language. Bodding translated both the Old Testament and New Testament of the Bible into the Santali language by 1914. Bodding's Santali writings are like "kuklí Puṭhi" (the Interrogation Book), "Sereñ Puṭhi" (Song Book), "Hoṛ Kañhi -ko" (Santali Folktales), "A Chapter on Santali Folklore", "Santali Folktales-I & II", "A Santali Dictionary- I, II, III, IV & V", "Materials for a Santali Grammar- I & II", "A Santali Grammar for Beginners", "Studies in Santal Medicine and Connected Folklore- I, II & III", "Traditional and Institutions of the Santals" (A translation of Mare Hapram Ko-reak Katha). Bodding collection which remains the world's largest collection of Santal culture and is currently owned and managed by the Museum of Cultural History and the National Library of Norway in Oslo.

JESUITS MISSIONARIES:

Belgian Jesuits arrived in Chotanagpur in 1869 and worked on land rights, education and evangelization among various tribes including Santals. They confronted zamindars, fought land alienation in courts and supported Adivasi communities against exploitation. Major Jesuits initiative mission work among the Santal started in 1924-25 under Calcutta province by Maltese and Sicilian Jesuits. Fr. Anthony Debono, a Maltese Jesuit is widely regarded as a pioneer. He arrived at Majlispur in March 1925, learned the Santali language and customs and began systematic work. However, unlike the Protestant missionaries the Jesuits missionaries are still on the ground working among the Santals and other tribes in India. The real motivation comes only from Gospel.

SALESIAN MISSIONARIES:

The Salesians commenced the missionary work among the

Santallate compare to other missionaries. Salesians took charge of Berhampore as their first parish in the Santal belt in 1928 under the Diocese of Krishnagar, West Bengal. The mission was revived as a residential parish in 1955 by Fr. Vincent Lazarro. Fr. John Topno and Bro. Joseph Topno are considered the pioneer of Santal mission in Murshidabad. Their missionary work was able to win the hearts and souls of many Santals. Salesian mission work among the Santal in west Bengal is huge success with a short period of time. At present, they are very much active and started many mission stations within Murshidabad districts.

CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES TO SANTAL IDENTITY:

The Santal before the advent of British and Christian missionaries, they maintained oral tradition which has been passed on from generation to generation. They maintained their social and political organisation. It was the British who documented their tradition and culture. Language is one of the great phenomenon that has been bone of contention among the Santal at present.

CONCLUSION:

The contribution of missionary work among the Santal tribe is immense. The noble work of Christian missionaries ignited and opened the eyes of the Santals themselves mainly who were associated with missionary activities to preserve their culture and traditions. However, in spite of their valuable contribution towards this community their work is being challenged by the heathens.

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